

ANALYSIS OF PRODUCT SAFETY INSPECTION METHODS AND STANDARDS

¹G.K.Solijonov

²A.O.Uzaydullaev (PhD)

³S.K.Kuzibekov (PhD)

¹National Metrology Institute of Uzbekistan

^{2,3}Gulistan State University

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ABSTRACT

The analysis of the device in the product safety testing laboratory, which leads to low accuracy of the test results, in the product quality inspection, most of the safety indicators are tested for various toxic and harmful conditions.

Product certification is carried out to assess the conformity of product characteristics, to verify the product's compliance with the technical and legal requirements of the relevant market, the establishment of a normative unit for international rules and norms models, parameters, dimensions and quality of production technology, testing and control methods, product including deployment, design and storage.

Pursuant to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6240 dated 02.06.2021 on the fundamental improvement of state management in the field of technical regulation, further deepening of structural reforms in the fields of standardization, certification and metrology, adaptation of the sector to international standards, wide use of standards in order to create an environment, to introduce modern methods to the processes of conformity assessment: obtaining a certificate of conformity for food and agricultural products, whose sanitary-epidemiological conclusion must be obtained in a mandatory manner, is carried out on a voluntary basis.

In this case, the preparers (manufacturers), suppliers and sellers of these products are responsible for ensuring their compliance with the mandatory requirements established by technical regulations and standards;

Technically, it is carried out by a regulatory agency or an authorized organization within its structure based on a risk analysis, keeping a list of products found to be non-compliant with technical regulations, standards and mandatory requirements established by law. Technically, it is carried out by a regulatory agency or an authorized organization within its structure.

The main purpose of international standards is to create a unified methodological basis for the development of new quality systems at the international level and the improvement of existing quality systems and their certification. Scientific and technical cooperation in the field

of standardization is aimed at coordinating the national standardization system with international, regional and progressive national standardization systems

Both backward countries and developed countries are equally interested in international standardization. Convergence of the quality level of products produced in different countries;

To facilitate mutual exchange of scientific and technical information and acceleration of scientific and technical development.

It makes it possible to speed up the introduction of advanced production methods, setting the requirements for the technical level and quality of products, raw materials, semi-finished products and components, as well as standards, requirements and methods in the field of product design and production.

Development of unification and aggregation of industrial products as the most important condition of production specialization; includes complex mechanization and automation of production processes, increasing the level of interchangeability, increasing the efficiency of product use and repair.

There are many product safety inspection projects and many risk factors in the regular commissioning and periodic inspection of laboratory equipment and supplies. Laboratory safety management and equipment troubleshooting are critical.

In product safety testing, it is applied to all kinds of strong acid and alkali, organic solvents and other flammable, explosive, highly corrosive and highly toxic chemical reagents.

In inspection, it is applied to high-pressure equipment such as microwave digestion equipment, sterilization vessels and various gas cylinders. In the actual application process, if inspectors' incompetent work leads to accidents such as safety and fire problems, inspectors' lives will pose a great risk to property safety. In the product safety testing laboratory, all types of instruments and equipment are delicate instruments that place high demands on reagents, environmental factors, and management methods. Therefore, in order to comprehensively improve the accuracy of the use of laboratory equipment, management personnel should carry out comprehensive management and maintenance, and should take good maintenance measures to avoid damage to the test equipment due to the influence of many factors.

Some equipment should require significant maintenance and repair costs. If the equipment does not take timely inspection and maintenance measures, the error of the test results will be more obvious. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out maintenance in time to increase the accuracy of the identification of tools and equipment.

Food testing standards have clear provisions on monitoring methods. Relevant technicians should use them wisely, use the instrument correctly, do a good job in debugging, implement the standard application and management of laboratory instruments and equipment, and improve the practical test results of the equipment.

When testing food products, the laboratory should be rationally arranged and various functional units should be installed.

For example, instrument analysis area, microbial detection area, routine testing and inspection area, logistics channel area, etc.

Among them, the food laboratory must analyze various inspection tasks, establish standardized inspection methods, rationally adjust all kinds of instruments and equipment,

install the most advanced detection methods, regularly conduct standardized inspection work, and improve inspection results.

The food inspection laboratory must fully comply with various new standards, control and manage the basic operation of the equipment, and improve the ability of technical personnel to solve unexpected problems.

It is necessary to analyze the general requirements for the qualification criteria and laboratory capabilities of inspection and testing facilities, establish standardized procedures, establish various operational guidelines, and establish standard management control points in various operational processes. Strengthening the software design and adapting the appropriate performance management method can help the comprehensive development of laboratory equipment and software.

In food safety inspection, a number of management processes are very complex and different requirements of different instructions for use must be followed. Due to the high complexity of the various inspection activities, there is a need to standardize the original operating procedures.

It is difficult to analyze the instrument in a food safety testing laboratory, which leads to low accuracy of test results, so debugging and management are necessary. In the food safety inspection, most of the safety indicators are tested for various toxic and harmful conditions.

Among them, pesticide residues, food additives, and illegal ingredients must be analyzed using a variety of tools. Such indicators require real verification. The output is low, but some tools are in trace amounts and

Micro-analysis, therefore debugging analysis of tools, is a difficult point for current quality control.

In general, in food testing, available test results have a greater impact on laboratory personnel and equipment.

Therefore, it is necessary to standardize the management of tools and equipment, improve the inspection ability of inspection personnel and the accuracy of food inspection, meet the development needs of society, improve food safety, and ensure personal safety and health. the masses.

Product safety certification is recognized by authorized local and national, retail community, project managers and assessors as a product that meets the requirements of compliance with applicable national safety standards.

Technical conditions for various products are determined by relevant legal norms, and authorized official institutions check whether products are manufactured in accordance with these technical regulations and their safety.

In this context, businesses must always offer reliable products to consumers. At the same time, providing information to consumers about the product, marking the products in such a way as to show the characteristics of the products, testing and analyzing the products released to the market when necessary, receiving and analyzing customer complaints, and providing the distribution companies with accurate results of audits. information about and collection and disposal of products.

Must take all necessary measures, including Similarly, distributors also offer dangerous products to consumers. and informing enterprises about the risks of the product in their activities and the necessary measures to protect against these risks.

Summary Purpose of Product Safety and Standards Review: In today's competitive environment, businesses need to pay more attention to their safety and standards to stay ahead. In order to protect its assets and achieve sustainable success, it must always work in accordance with standards and legal regulations. The main purpose of the standards is to create a unified methodological basis for the development of new quality systems at the international level and for the improvement of existing quality systems and their certification.

References:

1. «Метрология и стандартизация. Конспект лекций»: Сост. Т.В. Селеткова. Пермь: ГБПОУ ПКТС, 2018 - 175 с
2. Uzaydullaev, A. (2023). EXPERIMENTAL DETERMINATION OF THE DIELECTRIC PROPERTIES OF FRUITS (USING ULTRA-HIGH FREQUENCY (UHF) ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELD (EMM) ENERGY). *Science and innovation*, 2(A1), 217-221.
3. Kuzibekov, S. (2023). ANALYTICAL AND THEORETICAL STUDIES OF THE ASPIRATION AND FRACTIONATION PROCESS OF LOCAL SOYBEAN SEEDS. *Science and innovation*, 2(A1), 222-231.
4. Barakaev, N. R., & Kuzibekov, S. K. (2022). INVESTIGATION OF FLOW HYDRODYNAMICS IN THE PROCESS OF ASPIRATION CLEANING OF SOYBEAN SEEDS (GRAIN) ON A COMPUTER MODEL. *Harvard Educational and Scientific Review*, 2(2).
5. Rajabovich, B. N., Nusratillayevich, R. A., Tashpulatovich, K. M., & Komilovich, K. S. (2020). Improvement of the design of mobile equipment for post-harvest processing of agricultural crops. *Journal of critical reviews*, 7(14), 306-309.
6. Barakaev, N. R., Kurbanov, J. M., Uzaydullaev, A. O., & Gafforov, A. X. (2021, September). Qualitative purification of pomegranate juice using electro flotation. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 848, No. 1, p. 012024). IOP Publishing.
7. Nurmuxamedov, A., & Jankorazov, A. (2023). ANALYSIS OF THE METHODS OF IMPROVING THE FRYING PROCESS IN THE PRODUCTION OF VEGETABLE OILS. *Science and innovation*, 2(A1), 266-271.
8. Sattorov, K. K., & Nurmammedov, A. A. (2021). Jankorazov. AM, Choriev KR "Features of Triglycerides Isomerization in the Process of Hydrogenization of Cottonseed Oils" *International Journal of Disaster Recovery and Business Continuity*, 12(1), 990-997.
9. Nurmuxamedov, A., & Jankorazov, A. (2023). METHODS OF IMPROVING THE FRYING PROCESS IN THE PRODUCTION OF SOY OIL. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 3(4 Part 4), 41-48.
10. Хамдамов, М., Jankorazov, A., Hazratqulov, J., & Xidirova, S. (2023). STRUCTURE OF PROTEINS AND APPLICATION IN THE FIELD OF BIOTECHNOLOGY. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 3(4 Part 4), 212-220.

11. Jankorazov, A., Xolmamatova, D., & Murodboyeva, M. (2023). ENZYMES AND THEIR INDUSTRIAL APPLICATION METHODS. *International Bulletin of Engineering and Technology*, 3(3), 102-107.
12. Solijonov, G., Uzaydullaev, A., Kuzibekov, S., & Jankorazov, A. (2023). THE ROLE OF STANDARDIZATION IN THE INDUSTRY AND THE ANALYTICAL METHODS OF PRODUCT CERTIFICATION. *Science and innovation*, 2(A3), 144-149.
13. Javsurbek, K., Abror, J., Akhmad, N., & Shakir, I. (2023). REQUIREMENTS FOR THE QUALITY OF RAW MATERIALS PROCESSED IN THE INDUSTRY. *Universum: технические науки*, (1-4 (106)), 47-49.
14. Khazratkulov, J. Z., & Tashmurotov, A. N. (2023). STUDYING METHODS OF IMPROVING THE PROCESS OF APPLE JUICE PRODUCTION. *International Bulletin of Engineering and Technology*, 3(4), 38-42.
15. Karshievich, S. K., & Uli, K. J. Z. (2021). Dependence of the Content of Trans-Isomerized Fatty Acids on Hydrogenate Indicators. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 2(10), 27-30.
16. Jankorazov, A., Saydjanova, D., & Navro'zova, I. (2023). CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF SOY PLANT AND IMPROVING TECHNOLOGY OF OIL PROCESSING IN INDUSTRY. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 3(5 Part 2), 111-111
17. Yusupov, T. N., Solijonov, G. K., Uzaydullaev, A. O., Kuzibekov, S. K., & Jankorazov, A. M. (2023). METHODS OF STUDYING MEASUREMENTS AND ERRORS OF INTERNATIONAL STANDARD REQUIREMENTS. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 3(6 Part 2), 49-55.